

Creep Behaviour of Carbon-Epoxy $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2s}$ Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The viscoelastic properties of two carbon epoxy laminates have been studied by tensile creep on $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2s}$ coupons. The effect of temperature, moisture and stress have been reviewed. Irreversible deformation in creep may occur if moisture concentration and stress exceed a given limit.

INTRODUCTION

Properties of laminate fiber reinforced materials are a complex combination of fiber, matrix and interface behaviour. In a unidirectional composite longitudinal deformation is governed by fibers but shear and transverse deformation are matrix dependant. Although a proper design in a multidirectional laminates will allow primary stress to be sustained by the fiber, there are always stress component acting on the matrix by tensile (transverse) or shear loading. For this kind of stress component the polymeric nature of the matrix will induce viscoelastic behaviour. Time dependant phenomena are thus very often encountered in composite laminates.

Since the matrix play a dominant role in the transfer of stress, the intra laminar or interlaminar shear behaviour has to be carefully measured. This has been the subject of several mechanical test : torsion test, off axis tensile test, rail shear test, $(\pm 45^\circ)$ tensile test and short beam bending test. Among these test, tensile test on $(\pm 45^\circ)$ coupons appears to be the most suitable for viscoelastic measurements. Particularly tensile creep on these coupons will afford the time dependant shear modulus G_{12} from the formula proposed by ROSEN (1) :

$$G_{12} = \frac{\sigma_x}{2(\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y)}$$

x and y being the longitudinal and transverse direction. HALPIN (2) has utilized this test for the description of the compliance constants S_{ij} in function of time for Carbon-Epoxy and Glass-Epoxy composites.

In this paper we shall present results of creep test on Carbon -Epoxy composites and use of these experiments for the study of moisture effects. Water absorption has a pronounced effect on the composite mechanical behaviour through the plasticization of the matrix. The viscoelastic response is modified by a drop of glass transition temperature (3). Shear modulus decreases and creep is faster (4). However very few experiments have been done on moisture effect on creep properties. We have performed tensile creep test on ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{2s} coupons of two carbon-epoxy composites in a large range of moisture concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials are carbon epoxy laminates made from carbon fibre T300 and two epoxy resins , Narmco 5208 and Ciba BSL914. Samples were molded by the S.N.I.A.S company. The moisture conditioning was done at 90°C for different period of time depending of final desired concentration. Homogeneous distribution of moisture is obtained by maintaining the samples at 90°C in sealed containers. The moisture concentration is measured by weighing specially designed samples at the time of the experiment and after drying 24 hours at 120°C. The measured concentration is close to the expected one.

The ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{2s} tensile coupons are 25 mm wide and 200 mm long with carbon epoxy tabs leaving 60 mm of gage length.

The monotonic tensile test and the high stress creep test were performed on a servo hydraulic testing machine INSTRON 1341. The creep experiments were done on a specially modified ADAMEL creep machine with a heating system (20°C to 60°C). During all the tests, the longitudinal and the transverse deformation were measured with two modified INSTRON extensometers. The strain gages were not used for two reason : the strain for this type of laminate often exceed the gage capacity and the gage sticking may modify the moisture content in the zone under measurement.

In order to explore the three parameters, temperature, stress and humidity content, with the minimum of samples and a short time, the creep experiment has been performed with one sample for three temperatures or one sample for four or five levels of stress. Successive creep experiments may be performed if sufficient time is spend at zero stress between each experiment for the strain to become negligible (4 to 6 times the creep period).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Monotonic Tensile Tests

Results of monotonic tensile tests are given on Figure 1 and summarized in Table 1.

	T300 N 5208		T300 BSL 914	
Humidity	"dry"	1.62	"dry"	3.64
G ₁₂ GPa	6.1	5.2	5.20	4.12
τ _u MPa	103.5	98.5	85.0	77.0
γ _{12_u} %	4.0	7.2	7.2	13 %

Table 1

Fig. 1 - Shear stress-shear strain relationship in monotonic tensile test

Although the influence of moisture on shear modulus or shear strength is not very high, the increase of ultimate shear strain is typical of a plasticizing effect on the matrix.

Creep test at low and medium stress

Example of creep results for four stress levels and two moisture content in the case of T300 N 5208 are shown on Figure 2. The same results plotted on a log-log scale are shown on Figure 3. These plots may be described by a powerlaw :

$$\gamma_{12} = k t^n$$

where k and n are constants which depends of stress, humidity concentration and temperature. The variations of k and n with these three parameters are not simply described by phenomenological formula. Results may be summarized as follows :

- . k does not vary very much with temperature and/or humidity concentration (10 to 20 % in both case).
- . the variation of k versus the stress τ shows a significant non linear behaviour. This effect is much more pronounced for the high level of moisture content especially in the case of the BSL 914 resin.
- . the values of n extend from 0.013 to 0.045 for N5208 resin and from 0.012 to 0.085 for BSL 914 resin.
- . n increases with temperature, with moisture and with stress. The figures 4 and 5 summarizes results on Narmco N5208. From these figures it can be concluded that temperature has low influence on the exposant n. Figure 5 shows that shear stress has a significative influence on the n value. However the most important result is the effect of moisture which shows, except at the very low shear stress, a characteristic transition point around 1 to 1.2 %. In the case of BSL 914 the effect of temperature is much more pronounced but there are no evidence of a characteristic moisture concentration.

Fig. 2 - Creep curves at room temperature. T300-N5208

Fig. 3 - Log-Log plot of creep curves of figure 2

Fig. 4 - Influence of temperature on the exponent n. T300-N5208

Fig. 5 - Influence of stress on the exponent n. T300-N5208

Fig. 6 - Master curve of T300-N5208. Reference Temperature is 25°C. Reference Humidity concentration is zero. Shear stress is 34.5 MPa.

Fig. 7 - Master curve of T300-BSL914. Reference Temperature is 25°C. Reference Humidity concentration is zero. Shear stress is 31.1 MPa.

The effect of moisture and temperature may also be described with a master curve which is constructed by shifting on the log time scale the creep curves obtained for each temperature and each moisture concentration. This construction, well-known for the temperature effect (W.L.F), has been utilized for the moisture effect by CROSSMAN (5) and KIBLER (6) on carbon epoxy laminates.

Figures 6 and 7 shows the master curves for the two laminates we have studied. The shift factor a_H is a linear function of the moisture concentration. The dependance is higher if the temperature increases. The shift factor a_H is always greater for the T300-BSL 914 showing the high sensitivity to the water plasticizing effect on this material.

Creep test at high stress

The high stress creep experiment have been performed at a shear stress of 85 MPa for the T300 N 5208 material and 75 MPa for the T300 BSL 914. After a 100 seconds period of loading the creep strain is monitored during 500 second. At this time the sample is unloaded and the residual strain is monitored for 50 minutes. The results of the creep period confirm the previous measurements at lower stress. However the interesting result in this experiment is the variation of residual strain measured 50 minutes after unloading with the moisture

content. This is presented on figures 8 and 9 for the two materials. For the T300 N5208 composite at moisture level higher than 0.8 % the residual strain becomes very significant indicating that some irreversible process has occurred. For the T300 BSL 914 such a high stress induces irreversible deformation either at dry state and moisture enhances the phenomenon.

Fig. 8 - Irreversible strain in a 500 sec creep experiment. T300-N5208. Influence of humidity concentration. (22°C - τ = 85 MPa)

Fig. 9 - Irreversible strain in a 500 sec creep experiment. T300-BSL914. Influence of humidity concentration. (22°C - τ = 75 MPa)

DISCUSSION

The moisture absorption by the Epoxy matrix appears to have two effects : one, at low concentration, is a true plasticizing effect on the viscoelastic behaviour by lowering the glass transition temperature and enhancing the macromolecular mobility. The second effect, at high moisture concentration, involves an irreversible mechanism during the creep if the stress is greater than a given level (30 to 40 MPa in shear for the T300 N5208). This type of effect is difficult to explain. Two mechanisms may take place : the first is the chemical effect of water molecules on the hydrogen bonds in the epoxy resin. At high water concentration equilibrium of hydrogen bonding may be slightly displaced and a kind of "chemical creep" may occur. The second hypothesis is a damaging process which occurs at high stress for high level of moisture content. This damaging may be microcracks (or crazing ?) in the matrix or micro-decohesion at the interfaces. The observation of polished micrograph of the laminates has shown that microcrack exist at the interface for sample which has been stressed

at 65 MPa in shear. Thus this mechanism is likely to occur for high stress level but the question is still open for the range of stress from 30 to 65 MPa.

The fact that the distinction of these two types of moisture effect is not so evident for the laminates T300 BSL 914 is probably due to the two phases structures of this resin which contains over 30 % of polyethersulfone. These thermoplastic nodules enhance plastic deformation either at zero moisture level. Moisture at high concentration may also have an effect on the interface between thermoplastic nodules and epoxy resin.

CONCLUSION

This study on viscoelastic behaviour of two carbon-epoxy laminates has described the influence of temperature, moisture and stress on the time dependent shear modulus. Moisture concentration of around 1 % has been shown as a critical limit for the T300-N5208 laminates. Beyond this limit time dependent deformation occurs much more rapidly and at shear stress level higher than 50 % of UTS irreversible deformation take place during the creep.

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